

16th AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024):

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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PREFACE

Dear Colleagues,

The AgroStat biannual series of conference are driven by the Agro-Industry Group of the French Statistical Society (SFdS), which is a non-profit organisation bringing together researchers, engineers, teachers and statistics users (<https://www.sfds.asso.fr>). The 16th Edition of the AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024) will take place from the 3th to 6th September 2024 in the city of Bragança, Portugal, hosted and organised by the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança (IPB).

Bragança is a typically-Portuguese old town (Romanic origin dates back to the 10th century), located by the Natural Park of Montesinho – one of the wildest forest zones of Europe – and the Douro Valley – the third oldest protected wine region in the world; and surrounded by traditional villages of a distinctive rustic beauty. Bragança houses several traditional industries producing a myriad of local foods, such as cheese, fermented meats, wine, chestnuts and honey, which provide substantial economic sustainability to the region.

The AgroStat 2024 conference will reunite internationally recognised researchers and industrial organisations representatives, to take stock of advances in statistics, express their needs and to anticipate future challenges. The AgroStat 2024 conference will provide engineers, modellers, statisticians, developers and end-users, a unique opportunity to exchange knowledge and prospects around novel statistical methods applied to agri-food and sensory sciences. We expect to gather a significant number of delegates to participate in a comprehensive scientific programme that includes 5 keynote lectures, and oral communications, allocated in sessions focusing on the following themes: Sensometrics, Chemometrics, Experimental designs, Process control, Risk analysis, Big Data and Software tools.

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ANTI-LISTERIA EFFECT OF CITRUS PEEL EXTRACT IN FERMENTED MILK MODEL

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Listeria monocytogenes is a ubiquitous microorganism that can contaminate ready-to-eat foods since there is no bactericidal treatment between production and consumption. This pathogen has been identified as a potential contaminant in dairy products during post-processing steps. The objective of this work was to study the antibacterial effect of citrus limon peel extract on *L. monocytogenes* in a fermented milk model. Fermented milk was elaborated by using *L. paracasei* OWS 23 isolated and identified from spontaneous fermented milk. After fermentation, samples were individually inoculated with *L. monocytogenes* at ~5 log CFU/mL, freeze-dried Citrus limon extract was added at 2 folds Minimum Inhibitor Concentration level (2.5% (w/v)). The milk sample was stored at 4°C during 7 days. Kinetic curves of *L. monocytogenes* growth were adjusted with Weibull and Baranyi & Roberts models.

The correlation coefficient and standard error of fit were ranked from 0.7 - 0.95 and 0.18 - 0.28, respectively. The time required for a first tenfold reduction of the *L. monocytogenes* population (δ) at 4 °C from Weibull model was around 142.8 h in fermented milk without citrus lemon extract and 44.09 h in fermented milk supplemented with citrus limon extract. The total reduction of *L. monocytogenes* assessed using Baranyi and Roberts model was 1.005 log CFU/mL in fermented milk without citrus limon extract and 2.28 log CFU/mL in samples supplemented with citrus limon extract. Citrus limon extract may be considered as a promising natural bio-preservative that can be used in fermented milk.

Keywords: Fermented milk; *Listeria monocytogenes*; *L. paracasei* OWS 23; Citrus peel extract; Modelling

RECOVERY OF DIETARY FIBER AND POLYPHENOL FROM RED GRAPE MARC AND ASSESSMENT OF THEIR ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY AND POLYPHENOL COMPOSITION

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